

Table 2. Frequency distribution of selected genera of plant parasitic nematodes on rice in eastern India.

Type and no. of samples collected	<i>Meloidogyne</i>		<i>Hoplolaimus</i>		<i>Pratylenchus</i>		<i>Hirschmanniella</i>	
	Frequency	$\bar{x}^a$	Frequency	$\bar{x}$	Frequency	$\bar{x}$	Frequency	$\bar{x}$
<i>Upland rice - year one</i>								
Soil 61	18	221	16	42	22	94	20	68
Root 54	33	303	20	39	19	148	33	172
<i>Upland rice - year two</i>								
Soil 43	33	304	36	69	25	87	30	120
Root 38	30	408	30	111	24	263	25	20
<i>Rainfed lowland rice - year one</i>								
Soil 35	13	118	14	86	18	49	30	116
Root 42	21	279	11	195	7	198	32	479
<i>Rainfed lowland rice - year two</i>								
Soil 44	14	33	9	114	8	82	28	332
Root 44	29	212	27	373	26	388	20	622

^a $\bar{x}$ = larval and adult population/100 g soil or 1 g fresh weight of root tissue.

seedlings. We found that *Pratylenchus* and *M. graminicola* accounted for 7-18% of the nematode infestation of rice roots by the 4th day after infestation (DAI) and up to 40% by the 7th DAI.

Frequency of parasitic nematodes in the rhizosphere of upland rice in order of prevalence were genera *Meloidogyne*, *Pratylenchus*, *Hirschmanniella*, and *Hoplolaimus*; in rainfed lowland rice, *Hirschmanniella*, *Pratylenchus*, *Meloidogyne*, and *Hoplolaimus* (Table 2). ■

Farming systems

Effect of preceding crops on rice yield

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Rice was planted on about 2 million ha in the Punjab State, India, in 1991-92. Rice usually follows nonrice crops. We evaluated the yield and yield attributes of rice grown after crops of wheat, winter maize, field pea - green gram, Swede rape - green gram, potato - transplanted winter maize, Indian rape - transplanted Swede rape - green gram, potato - sunflower, and Indian rape - sunflower

from 1988 to 1992 in fixed plots laid out in randomized block design. Intensity of the crop rotations ranged from 200 to 400%.

Soil of the experimental field was calcareous, sandy loam with pH 8.1 and 0.28% organic C. All crops received the recommended fertilizer package and practices except sunflower after potato, which was grown without applied fertilizers.

Mean grain yield of rice following wheat was lowest at 4.8 t/ha. Maximum rice yield of 6.5 t/ha was obtained in potato - transplanted winter maize - rice sequence, although it was at par with rice yield from Swede rape - green gram - rice and potato - sunflower - rice systems.

These cropping systems produced significantly higher rice yield, effective tillers, panicle lengths, and test weights than the other systems (see table).

Winter maize - rice, field pea - green gram - rice, Indian rape - transplanted Swede rape - green gram - rice, and Indian rape - sunflower - rice systems all produced about 5.2 t rice/ha.

Farmers can obtain higher rice productivity by selecting suitable preceding cropping systems, such as potato - transplanted winter maize, Swede rape - green gram, and potato - sunflower. These systems can also help improve soil fertility and contribute to crop diversification. ■

Effect of preceding crops on yield attributes and grain yield of rice. Punjab, India, 1988-92.

Preceding crops	Grain yield (t/ha)					Effective tillers/plant (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	200-grain weight (g)
	1988-89	1989-90	1990-91	1991-92	Mean			
Wheat	5.0	5.9	5.6	3.4	4.8	8.5	22.4	5.25
Winter maize	5.4	6.2	5.7	3.7	5.2	8.6	23.0	5.25
Field pea - green gram	5.6	6.0	5.2	3.9	5.2	8.1	22.8	5.25
Swede rape - green gram	6.6	7.1	6.6	5.2	6.2	9.5	23.7	5.50
Potato - transplanted winter maize	6.8	7.4	6.6	5.9	6.5	9.6	23.7	5.75
Indian rape - transplanted Swede rape - green gram	4.0	6.9	5.4	4.8	5.2	8.8	22.2	5.50
Potato - sunflower	6.5	7.0	6.3	6.0	6.2	9.6	23.9	6.00
Indian rape - sunflower	3.7	7.0	5.5	4.7	5.2	8.2	22.7	5.25
LSD (0.05)	0.6	0.3	0.8	0.9	0.6	0.8	1.2	0.60